

Contribution of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) to the Diagnosis of Progressive Supranuclear Palsy: A Case Report

Sarah Slimani^{1*}, Hajar Belghacham¹, Kaoutar Hjjiej¹, Mohamed Amine Mnaili¹, Youssouf Ben Moh¹, Ahmed Bourazza¹

¹Neurology Department, Mohammed V Military Teaching Hospital, Rabat, Morocco

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***Corresponding author:** Sarah Slimani, Neurology Department, Mohammed V Military Teaching Hospital, Rabat, Morocco

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson-plus syndromes are neurodegenerative disorders resembling Parkinson's disease with additional features and faster progression, among which progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) is a major subtype. We report a 65-year-old man with progressive gait disturbance, recurrent falls, and cognitive impairment, whose examination revealed axial rigidity and vertical gaze palsy. Brain MRI showed characteristic midbrain atrophy with “Hummingbird”, “Mickey Mouse” and “Morning Glory” signs, supporting a diagnosis of probable PSP. Despite symptomatic treatment, the patient showed no improvement and died following a fall-related intracranial hemorrhage. Diagnosis of PSP remains primarily clinical, with MRI providing supportive but not definitive diagnostic value.

Keywords: Progressive supranuclear palsy; Neurodegenerative disorder; Hummingbird sign; Mickey Mouse sign; Morning Glory sign

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson-plus syndromes, also referred to as atypical parkinsonian disorders, are a group of neurodegenerative conditions that clinically resemble Parkinson's disease—characterized by bradykinesia, rigidity, and tremor—but are distinguished by additional specific clinical features, a poor or limited therapeutic response to levodopa, and a more rapid disease progression.^[1]

The most extensively characterized subtypes include progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP), multiple system atrophy (MSA), corticobasal degeneration (CBD), and dementia with Lewy bodies.

PSP represents the second most common form of neurodegenerative parkinsonism, following idiopathic Parkinson's disease.^[2]

We here report the case of a 65-years old patient in whom the diagnosis of PSP was retained based on his clinical status including postural instability, oculomotor and cognitive dysfunction and on brain MRI data showing the characteristic “hummingbird” and “Mickey mouse” signs.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 65-year-old male patient with a medical history of type 2 diabetes managed with oral antidiabetic agents, hypertension under treatment, dyslipidemia treated with statins, and benign prostatic hyperplasia presented with gait disturbances. The onset of symptoms dated back approximately to three years, beginning with a progressive impairment of gait and balance, accompanied by recurrent, unexplained falls occurring both backward and forward and memory disturbances. The clinical course was characterized by a gradual worsening of these symptoms.

Neurological examination revealed a hypomimic facies and a short-stepped, ataxic gait on straight-line walking. The Romberg sign was negative, and no sensory or motor deficits were identified. Muscle tone examination demonstrated plastic rigidity with a cogwheel phenomenon. There was no evidence of limb incoordination. Oculomotor assessment showed vertical saccade, and vertical gaze palsy. Regarding higher cortical functions, there was no evidence of aphasia, apraxia, or agnosia. Cognitive assessment using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) yielded a score of 20/30, with points lost for visuospatial/executive, attention, and verbal fluency items.

His symptoms were evaluated with MRI of the brain.

The MRI demonstrated midbrain atrophy([Figure 1](#)), with Hummingbird, Mickey Mouse and Morning Glory Signs. There was no evidence of diffusion restriction or abnormal contrast enhancement. These findings were suggestive of progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) and argued against alternative diagnoses such as Parkinson’s disease and multiple system atrophy.

Laboratory results of thyroid function tests, vitamin B12, folate, and vitamin D levels, inflammatory markers, autoimmune screening, infectious serologies (hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, syphilis, and HIV), and serum protein electrophoresis were all normal.

Symptomatic therapy was initiated however no significant clinical improvement was observed. The patient died five months later from an acute subdural hematoma associated with secondary subarachnoid hemorrhage, occurring in the context of a fall.

Figure 1: MRI of the brain.

A: Sagittal T1WI image showing midbrain atrophy which is demonstrated as hummingbird sign (red arrows).

B: Axial fluid-attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR) MRI showing concave lateral margins of the midbrain (morning glory sign, pink arrows) and reduced midline anteroposterior midbrain diameter (yellow line) at the level of superior colliculi (mickey mouse sign).

C: Axial FLAIR image shows diffuse cortical atrophy.

DISCUSSION

Progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) is an uncommon neurodegenerative disorder within the spectrum of Parkinson-plus syndromes.

PSP has a prevalence of 5 to 7 per 100,000. The annual incidence increases with age (the key risk factor identified to date) from about 2 per 100,000 in the sixth decade of life to about 15 per 100,000 in the ninth decade.^[3] It is characterized by abnormal tau protein accumulation in both neurons and glial cells, predominantly isoforms containing four microtubule-binding repeats (4R tau).^[4] This primary tauopathy results in progressive degeneration of the brainstem, basal ganglia, and frontal cortex, leading to rapidly evolving motor, cognitive, and behavioral impairment.^[4] The frequent delay in diagnosis highlights its significant clinical and research importance.

Clinically, it presents with vertical supranuclear gaze palsy, early axial rigidity, unexplained falls, and frontal cognitive impairment, with limited responsiveness to levodopa. Diagnosis is essentially clinical and assisted by neuroimaging

In 2017, the International Parkinson and Movement Disorder Society proposed revised clinical diagnostic criteria for PSP, acknowledging the spectrum of clinical phenotypes associated with the disorder.^[5,6] According to it, our patient had a probable PSP with predominant postural instability (PSP-PI).

MRI plays an important role in supporting the diagnosis of PSP through the identification of characteristic imaging signs and quantitative indices.

Midbrain atrophy is the classic hallmark of PSP and is traditionally recognized by the “hummingbird sign” at the superior aspect of the midbrain, the “Mickey Mouse” appearance of the anteroposterior midline diameter of the midbrain at the level of the superior colliculus, and the “morning glory” sign, reflecting loss of the lateral convex contour of the midbrain tegmentum.^[7-9] These imaging features can also be quantified through volumetric assessment of subcortical structures, particularly demonstrating atrophy of the midbrain, pons, and superior cerebellar peduncles (SCP), along with associated ventricular enlargement.

In a blinded analysis of MRI scans from 48 postmortem cases with neuropathological confirmation (including progressive supranuclear palsy, multiple system atrophy, Parkinson’s disease, corticobasal degeneration, and controls), Massey et al. demonstrated that the “hummingbird” and “morning glory” signs were highly specific for progressive supranuclear palsy but exhibited limited sensitivity. Furthermore, MRI evaluation, clinical diagnosis, and macroscopic postmortem examination showed comparable sensitivity and specificity in predicting the definitive neuropathological diagnosis.^[10]

Two independent cohorts with neuropathological confirmation have demonstrated that a midsagittal midbrain-to-pontine base distance ratio of <0.5 on T1-weighted MRI is a highly sensitive and specific marker for progressive supranuclear palsy.^[11,12]

Advanced imaging biomarkers used in the assessment of PSP include MRI-based structural volumetry to evaluate regional brain atrophy, particularly within the midbrain; cortical thickness analysis to quantify cortical gray matter loss; diffusion MRI to assess white matter microstructural alterations; neuromelanin-sensitive MRI to detect structural and molecular changes in the midbrain; tau PET imaging to measure the accumulation of pathological tau species; and DaTscan SPECT or DaT PET to evaluate changes in presynaptic dopaminergic terminal density.^[13]

These advanced neuroimaging modalities were not performed for our patient.

Treatment is symptomatic and multidisciplinary.

A therapeutic trial of levodopa is recommended for all patients with PSP to address parkinsonian features. Dopaminergic medications other than levodopa are generally discouraged due to limited therapeutic benefit and an unfavorable adverse-effect profile. Likewise, anticholinergic drugs should be avoided whenever feasible, given their potential to exacerbate cognitive dysfunction.

Depressive and anxiety symptoms are frequently observed in progressive supranuclear palsy; selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) may be beneficial at conventional dosages. Modafinil or methylphenidate can be considered for the management of apathy. Botulinum toxin injections may provide symptomatic relief across a spectrum of manifestations, including sialorrhea, cervical and limb dystonia or spasticity, and associated pain.

Rehabilitative interventions are fundamental to preserving and optimizing functional capacity in PSP and should be implemented continuously during the disease trajectory. In particular, physiotherapy focuses on gait and postural stability training, as well as strategies for fall prevention.

Emerging anti-tau therapies show promise but lack robust clinical evidence.^[4] Despite two recent negative clinical trials of anti-tau monoclonal antibodies in progressive supranuclear palsy (tilavonemab and gosuranemab), emerging therapeutic avenues remain promising. The microtubule-binding domain–targeting anti-tau agent bepranemab is currently under evaluation in Europe, and the Rho-kinase inhibitor fasudil is also being investigated as a potential treatment.^[14,15]

PSP is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by relentless progression, marked impairment in quality of life, and increasing dependence in activities of daily living. Early postural instability with falls, cognitive impairment, and early-onset dysphagia are significant predictors of survival, whereas supranuclear gaze palsy and responsiveness to levodopa do not appear to be clearly associated with prognosis.^[16]

CONCLUSION

Currently, imaging findings are regarded as supportive rather than core criteria for the clinical diagnosis of PSP; however, their diagnostic relevance and utility may become more prominent in the future. neuroimaging techniques can substantially improve diagnostic certainty in appropriately selected clinical contexts and may enable earlier detection, which is critical for optimizing management strategies and informing prognosis.

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